

Translation Techniques of Emotive Language in the “Barbie Mermaid Power” Movie

¹Rosa Nailahimmah Ulya, ²Raden Arief Nugroho

¹Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, Semarang, Indonesia

²Universitas Dian Nuswantoro, Semarang, Indonesia

311202202452@mhs.dinus.ac.id

Abstract. Translation is a kind of communication specially to understand language that's not mother tongue. The process of translation while translating foreign language to mother tongue also needed idea of creativity while translating to the others. The focus of this research to analyses translation techniques and theory of emotive in movie Barbie Mermaid Power on Netflix, 2022. In this case of translating, translators good with right brain, because this isn't about language but about how the translators look emotionally because this research about theory of emotive, so this research can be understandable for readers. The translations techniques itself is a procedure to analyze and classify how translation equivalent work. The most data of translations techniques in this research found is established equivalent (9) with the percentage 45%, the least techniques found is generalization (1) with the percentage is. The data of theory emotive are average count of percentage there are shocked (1), sad (1) and angry (1) with the same percentage is 33%.

Keywords: translation; language; techniques; theory; emotive.

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Nugroho et al. (2016) defines translation as translating the meaning of a text into another language according to what the author intended. In other words, translation is an effort to replace the source language text with equivalent text in the target language. Second, what is translated is the meaning as intended by the author (Astiningsih & Nugroho, 2024; Meilany & Nugroho, 2024). The purpose is to know in the general what the content or words of the text are. For this purpose, it certainly does not require a perfect translation. In translation text or other must be clear and understandable for the readers. Sometimes, translation text needed some examples, classification, and description about what the translator means or about what the source text mean (Basari & Nugroho, 2017; Nugroho et al., 2020). The quality of translation required is accuracy to ensure that you receive the right message and the right information (Iriawan & Nugroho, 2023; Muhaya & Nugroho, 2024).

A translator must understand and know well about the context of the text to be translated. So, readers can understand the meaning of translated text. Readers must also understand the language and the meaning of the source text, also the context of translated text (Pratama et al., 2021; Normalita & Nugroho, 2023). Translators must know and have a knowledge about translation techniques, because in every translator work or translated text, subtitle, or essay they must know about translation techniques first. According to Molina and Albir (2012) there are 18 types of translation techniques, there are Amplification, Borrowing, Compensation, Discursive Creation, Established Equivalent, Literal Translation, Modulation, Reduction, Transposition, Paraphrase, Particularization, Variation, Generalization, Calque, Description, Adaptation, and Substitution. In this research also use theory of emotive in the movie Barbie: Mermaid Power on Netflix. There are six emotive types according to Ekman (1972), such as happy, sad, angry, scared, disgusted, and shocked.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Translation Techniques

1. Adaptation
In the technique translation contains cultural element that changes from sources language to target language, but have the similar meanings (Isnaini & Nugroho, 2022).
2. Amplification
The technique adds some detail of information that's not available in the source language. This technique helps translator to give information about source text to readers, so readers can be more understandable with the target language (Muhaya & Nugroho, 2024).
3. Borrowing
Translation technique that uses words that uses words or phrases from the source language in the target language. Borrowing can be pure borrowing, which is borrowing without making any changes (Nugroho & Basari, 2019).
4. Calque
The technique translated of word or phrase in the source language into target language (Nugroho, et al. 2019).
5. Compensation
Translation technique that replace the position of information elements or stylish effects in source language in another part of target language, because it cannot be realized in the same part in target language (Sitio & Nugroho, 2023).
6. Description
Translation technique that replaces a term in the source language with its description in the target language. This technique is used when a term in the source language does not have an equivalent term in the target language (Shafira & Nugroho, 2023).
7. Discursive Creation
Translation technique that uses temporary equivalents that are far from the original context. This technique often appears in translating film, book, and novel titles (Pangaksmi & Nugroho, 2023).
8. Established Equivalent
Translation technique that translated terms in the source language with terms that is common in the target language. The terms in the source language are generally based on dictionary or everyday expressions (Nugroho et al., 2022).
9. Generalization
This translation technique is translating a term into a term that common and widely known by public. This technique is used when a term in source language refers to a specific part, the equivalent of which in the target language does not refer to the same part (Suryaningtyas et al., 2019).
10. Linguistics Amplification
Translation technique that adds linguistic elements of the source language text into the target language text. This technique is often used in interpreting or dubbing (Shalekah et al, 2020).
11. Linguistics Compression
Translation technique that unites or combines linguistic elements in source language texts. This technique is often used in interpreting or dubbing (Nugroho et al, 2016).
12. Literal Translation
Translation technique that translates an expression in the source language word of word into the target language (Larassati et al., 2019).
13. Modulation
Translation technique that replace the focus, point of view or cognitive aspects in source language in the source language, either lexically or structurally (Nugroho et al, 2016).
14. Particularization

Translation technique that uses more concrete and specific terms. This technique is the opposite of generalization technique (Shalekah et al, 2020).

15. Reduction

Condensing information contained in the source language into the target language. The information compression carried out must not change the message in the source language text (Pangaksmi & Nugroho, 2023).

16. Substitution

Changing linguistics elements to paralinguistic, such as intonation and gestures or otherwise (Shafira & Nugroho, 2023).

17. Transposition

Translation technique that replaces the grammatical category of the source language in the target language, the example changing words into phrases. This technique usually used because of the grammatical differences between the source language and target language (Nugroho & Basari, 2019).

18. Variation

Translation technique that replace linguistic and paralinguistic elements that influence linguistic variation. The example, changes in textual tone, style, geographical dialect and social dialect (Isnaini & Nugroho, 2022).

Emotive language

Emotion is a complex reaction that contains high degree of activity and changes in the physical and is related to strong feelings and often changes in behavior. (Chaplin in Walgito, 2003).

Emotions can be controlled. According to Ekman and Friesen, there are 3 types of display rules, namely:

1. Masking: a person's condition that can hide the emotions they experience.
2. Modulation: a person's condition that cannot completely suppress their physical symptoms.
3. Simulation: a person who does not experience emotions but seems to experience emotions.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

Fitria (2015) Translation Techniques of English to Indonesian Subtitle in Doraemon 'Stand by Me' Movie

This research is to classify types of translation techniques from movie Doraemon “Stand by Me” English – Indonesian subtitle, and analysis in term of accuracy, acceptability and readability.

Tawami (2018) Propositional Analysis of Emotive Word Characters in Animation Movie

This research examines the study of linguistic language associated with emotive language in one of the characters in an animated film. This research contains the propositional structure of each character's emotive word.

Fitria (2020) Translation Techniques of English to Indonesian Subtitle in “Crazy Rich Asian” Movie

This research is to classify the dominant type of translation techniques from English-Indonesian subtitle. Based on accurate data of translation techniques that found in movie “Crazy Rich Asian”.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method of this study is use descriptive qualitative method. Descriptive qualitative method is a research method that focuses on understanding phenomenon by examining their characteristics and quality of this characteristics (Nugroho, 2010). This type of research is used when want to explore some topic that has never been studied in depth before, or when want to gain a better understanding

of some topic that has been studied previously but use a different perspective and gain valuable insight in the process. This study uses qualitative method to explain the translation techniques and theory emotive in the movie of Barbie: Mermaid Power. The data found from this movie by watching Barbie: Mermaid Power on Netflix. This movie was directed by Emory Ronald “Ron” Myrick and written by Ann Austen and this movie has translated by Netflix automatics. The movie was shown for the first time on Netflix August 17, 2022 with the duration 1 hour 5 minutes or 65 minutes.

The data collection technique in this research uses descriptive data analysis techniques, by collecting data from the Barbie Mermaid Power movie then collecting all and classifying them into table translation techniques and emotive language. then the data is explained by taking several examples of the data found (Nababan et al., 2012).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 translation techniques

No.	Translation Techniques	Findings	Percentage (%)
1.	Established Equivalent	9	45%
2.	Variation	5	25%
3.	Reduction	3	15%
4	Literal Translation	2	10%
5.	Generalization	1	5%

Table 2 emotive language

No.	Emotive language	Findings	Percentage(%)
1.	Shocked	1	33,3%
2.	Sad	1	33,3%
3.	Angry	1	33,3%

Excerpt 1:

ST: “We’re here to pick up trash, not seaweed”

TT: “Kita memungut sampah, bukan rumput laut”

There is Established Equivalent because is a common that use a term or expression that is already

common in the target language. The context of the excerpt 1 is, there are Brooklyn Barbie, her sisters, and Malibu Barbie has to cleaning the ocean, because there are have so many trash to be cleaned.

Excerpt 2:

ST : "My bad"

TT: "Maaf"

There is Variation because "My bad" can be translated to *ini salahku*, *maafkan aku*, and etc. The context of this excerpt is when Skipper thrown seaweed to Brooklyn Barbie and Malibu Barbie, while they are have to clean the ocean.

Excerpt 3:

ST: "A mermaid? You know that sounds crazy right?"

TT: "Duyung? Kau tahu itu terdengar konyol, kan?"

There is a emotive language of shocked, because the Brooklyn Barbie have a tell them about her glowing necklace, the glowing necklace it is mean mermaid need Barbie help, but Malibu Barbie didn't believe it, so her have shocked.

Excerpt 4:

ST: "Well, it was a good gig while it lasted"

TT: "*Kerjanya bagus, meski singkat*"

There is Reduction because the word "Well", is not translated into target text. The context of this excerpt is while Marlo isn't done with her project, and Marlo mad to her assistant.

Excerpt 5:

ST: "I'm seven, and I'm obsessed with mermaid. Do you have to ask?"

TT: "Usiaku tujuh tahun dan aku terobsesi duyung. Kau harus bertanya?"

There is a generalization because the translator translated it into general in target text, the translator added the word *usiaku* in target text, because it will be understandable by the readers. The context of the excerpt is while Brooklyn Barbie have to ask Chelsea to join with them help mermaid..

CONCLUSION

Based on finding the data of techniques of translation and theory of emotive in movie of Barbie Mermaid Power, there were found five type of translation techniques, the translation techniques found from 20 data in this movie. There are Established Equivalent, this is the most translation techniques found with percentage is 45% from 9 data. Then Variation with the percentage 25% from 5 data. Reduction with the percentage 15% from 3 data. Literal Translation with the percentage 10% from 2 data. The least data of translation techniques found is Generalization with the percentage is 5% from 1 data. The theory emotive found is shocked, sad, and angry, each theory emotive have percentage 33,3% from 1 data in each type.

REFERENCES

- Astiningsih, D.A. and Nugroho, R.A. (2024). Analysis of Micro Translation Strategies Used by the Main Character in Subtitle Conversation Movie “Guardians of the Galaxy Vol 2”. *JELTL (Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics)*, Vol. 9(1), 2024.
- Basari, A. and Nugroho, R.A. (2017). The Use of Aegisub in Teaching Audiovisual Translation Classes: A Review On IT-Based Subtitling Course. *The 1st Education and Language International Conference Proceedings Center for International Language Development of Unissula*.
- Iriawan, K.N.P. and Nugroho, R.A. (2023). Translation Techniques of the Complex Sentences in Bilingual Textbook Science Biology 3 for Junior High School Grade IX Published by Erlangga. *International Journal of Education and Literature*, Vol. 2(3), 2023.
- Isnaini, F. and Nugroho, R.A. (2022). Translation Analysis of Accusation Expression in Moriarty The Patriot Comic. *Proceedings of UNCLLE (Undergraduate Conference on Language, Literature, and Culture) 2022*, Vol. 2(1), 174-181.
- Larassati, A., Setyaningsih, N., Nugroho, R.A., Suryaningtyas, V.W., Cahyono, S.P. and Pamelasari, S.D. (2019). Google vs. Instagram Machine Translation: Multilingual Application Program Interface Errors in Translating Procedure Text Genre. *Proceedings - 2019 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Industry 4.0: Retrospect, Prospect, and Challenges, iSemantic 2019*. DOI: 10.1109/ISEMANTIC.2019.8884334
- Meilany, D.A. and Nugroho, R.A. (2024). Conversation Analysis between Shakira and Jimmy Fallon "Shakira's Music Teacher Wouldn't Let Her Join the School Choir" At the Tonight Show. *Paramasastra: Jurnal Ilmiah Bahasa Sastra dan Pembelajarannya*, Vol. 11(1), 2024.
- Muhaya, R.E. and Nugroho, R.A. (2024). Features of Legal Language and Its Translation Analysis in Indonesian-English “Settlement Termination Agreement”. *JELTL (Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics)*, Vol. 9(1), 2024.
- Nababan, M.N., Nuraeni, A., and Sumardiono. (2012). Pengembangan Model Penilaian Kualitas Terjemahan. *Kajian Linguistik and Sastra*, 24(1).
- Normalita, A. and Nugroho, R.A. (2023). Changing the “Body” of BBC News: a Study of News Headlines Translation Techniques. *5th International Conference on Language, Linguistics, and Literature (COLALITE 2023)*. Atlantis Press.
- Nugroho, R.A. and Basari, A. (2019). Translation Course 4.0 Redefined: Enhancing Work Efficiency and Meaning Accuracy Using AEGISUB 3.2. 2 Subtitling Software. *Proceedings - 2019 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Industry 4.0: Retrospect, Prospect, and Challenges, iSemantic 2019*, 225–231.
- Nugroho, R.A., Basari, A., Suryaningtyas, V.W., Cahyono, S.P. (2020). University Students’ Perception of Online Learning in Covid-19 Pandemic: A Case Study in a Translation Course. *Proceedings - 2020 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication, iSemantic 2020*, 548–553.

- Nugroho, R.A., Basari, A., Suryaningtyas, V.W., Setyaningsih, N., Cahyono, S.P., and Larassati, A. (2019). Translation as an Alternative to a Language-Based Vocational Course at the Undergraduate Level. *1st Vocational Education International Conference (VEIC 2019)*. Atlantis Press.
- Nugroho, R.A., Muljono, and Nababan, M.R. (2022). Accuracy in Translations by Visually-Impaired Students and Its Implications for Competence and Improvement Aspects. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 12(9).
- Nugroho, R.A., Nababan, M.R., and Subroto, E.D. (2016). Translation Microstrategies Used by Visually Impaired Translators. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 6(5).
- Nugroho, R.A. (2010). Rapport and Address Terms in Family Guy Cartoon: Can (Targeted) Audience Identify a Social Dimension of Relationship? *Journal LITE* 6(2). Retrieved from: <https://publikasi.dinus.ac.id/index.php/lite/article/download/490/993>
- Pangaksmi, O.A. and Nugroho, R.A. (2023). Discovering the Identity of Pun in English and Indonesian Subtitles: A Study of Pun Translation Strategies in “The SpongeBob Movie: Sponge on the Run”. *5th International Conference on Language, Linguistics, and Literature (COLALITE 2023)*. Atlantis Press.
- Pratama, A.A., Ramadhan, T.B.L, Elawati, F.N., and Nugroho, R.A. (2021). Translation Quality Analysis of Cultural Words in Translated Tourism Promotional Text of Central Java. *JELTL (Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics)*, Vol. 6(1), 2021.
- Shafira, D.B. and Nugroho, R.A. (2023). Translation Error Types Analysis on TikTok Indonesian-English Auto-Translation Content. *International Seminar SEMANTIKS & PRASASTI 2023 Theme: Language in the Workplace (PRASASTI 2023)*. Atlantis Press.
- Shalekhah, R.A., Estayani, S.A., Sari, M., Nugroho, R.A. (2020). Linguistic Politeness Analysis of Indonesia’s Prominent YouTube Influencers. *JELTL (Journal of English Language Teaching and Linguistics)*, Vol. 5(3), 2020.
- Sitio, T.J. and Nugroho, R.A. (2023). Translation Techniques of Apologize Expressions on Enola Holmes Vol. 2 Movie. *Proceedings of UNCLLE (Undergraduate Conference on Language, Literature, and Culture) 2023*, Vol. 3(1), 466-475.
- Suryaningtyas, V.W., Nugroho, R.A., Cahyono, S.P., Nababan, M.R., and Santosa, R. (2019). Translation Learning Enrichment Using Smart Application Creator 3.0: An Attempt to Design a Mobile Application in Translation for Tourism Purpose Course. *Proceedings - 2019 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Industry 4.0: Retrospect, Prospect, and Challenges, iSemantic 2019*, 542–547.
- Tawami, T. (2018). *Propositional Analysis of Emotive-Word Characters in Animation Movie. International Conference on Business, Economic, Science and Humanities (ICOBEST 2018)*, 78-80, 2018.
- Fitriani, T.N. (2015). *Translation Techniques of English to Indonesian Subtitle in Doraemon ‘Stand by Me’*. SSRN, 2015

Fitriani, T.N. (2020). *Translation Technique of English to Indonesian Subtitle in “Crazy Rich Asian” Movie. ELS Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities 3 (1), 51-65, 2020.*